

Movement Guided PCG in the 2D Platformer *Roast in Pieces*

Fridolin Ernst

Master's Degree Program Artificial Intelligence Engineering
University of Applied Sciences Technikum Wien
Vienna, Austria
ai24m038@technikum-wien.at

Markus Petz

Department of Computer Science and Applied Mathematics
University of Applied Sciences Technikum Wien
Vienna, Austria
petzm@technikum-wien.at

Christoph Redl

Department of Computer Science and Applied Mathematics
University of Applied Sciences Technikum Wien
Vienna, Austria
redlch@technikum-wien.at

Abstract—Procedural Content Generation (PCG) is commonly used to improve replayability and reduce development effort, but fewer approaches focus on lightweight adaptive systems that modify existing environments based on player behaviour. This work presents an adaptive obstacle placement system for a 2D platformer that uses player movement heatmaps to guide future obstacle placement with lethality and attack-range constraints. The approach can be extended to other 2D and 3D game environments.

Implemented in *Roast in Pieces*, the system was evaluated in a within-subjects study with 24 participants, comparing adaptive and random placement using non-parametric statistical analysis.

The adaptive system significantly increased perceived difficulty ($p = 0.0050$) and path obstruction ($p < 0.0001$). Telemetry showed reduced progression via resource collection ($p = 0.0012$). No significant differences were found for enjoyment ($p = 0.6579$) or preference ($p = 0.1516$).

Overall, movement-driven adaptation increased challenge and interaction but did not improve player satisfaction, suggesting future PCG systems should incorporate player competence alongside behavioural data.

Index Terms—Procedural Content Generation, Adaptive Game Mechanics, Player Modelling, Dynamic Game Environments, Game AI, Player Experience, 2D Platformers

I. INTRODUCTION

This section introduces the game *Roast in Pieces*, which serves as the test environment for the proposed adaptive obstacle placement system. It then presents the motivation for the research, discusses related approaches in procedural content generation and player-adaptive systems, and outlines the objectives of the study.

A. *Roast in Pieces*

Roast in Pieces is a fast-paced 2D local multiplayer party platformer survival game designed for 2–4 players. In the game, players control burning marshmallow characters and compete against each other in short, chaotic rounds. Continuous fire damage creates constant pressure and requires quick reactions. To counteract this, players can collect milk

Fig. 1. Screenshot of *Roast in Pieces*

to temporarily stop the damage and prolong survival. Additionally, power-ups can be acquired, and objects can be placed strategically within the arena to hinder opponents. The objective of each round is to outlast the other players and survive to become the last remaining marshmallow.

B. Motivation

Procedural content generation (PCG) has become an important area of research in digital games due to its potential to increase replayability, reduce development effort, and create more varied gameplay experiences.

Prior work has explored a wide range of PCG techniques, including search-based methods, machine learning approaches, and systems that incorporate player behaviour or preferences. In addition, Dynamic Difficulty Adjustment (DDA) and personalization systems demonstrate the benefits of adapting gameplay to individual players.

However, most existing approaches focus on either generating entire levels, training complex models, or adjusting high-level difficulty parameters. Comparatively little research has investigated lightweight systems that incrementally modify

existing game environments during gameplay based directly on observed player behaviour.

This work addresses this gap by proposing an adaptive obstacle placement system that uses player movement patterns collected during gameplay. Instead of generating new levels, the system continuously adapts the existing environment by repositioning obstacles according to movement heatmaps while enforcing constraints to maintain fairness and playability.

This form of adaptivity aims to preserve core GameFlow aspects such as challenge, skill balance, and feedback [1]. By reacting to player movement patterns over time, the system encourages adaptation in player strategy across multiple rounds and provides implicit feedback through visible environmental changes.

The approach is particularly relevant for games with repeated traversal of similar spaces, such as metroidvania or roguelike titles like *Hollow Knight*, *Hades*, and *Rain World*. In such contexts, static or weakly adaptive content can lead to reduced engagement once player skill increases beyond the designed challenge level [2].

The primary objective of this work is to evaluate whether movement-driven adaptive obstacle placement leads to improved enjoyment, engagement, and perceived challenge compared to random placement, using both subjective evaluation and gameplay telemetry.

II. METHODS

This section presents the methodological framework of the work based on Design Science Research (DSR) and describes the study design and evaluation approach used to assess the proposed system.

A. Research Design

This work follows the Design Science Research (DSR) methodology, which structures the research process into six activities: problem identification, definition of objectives, design and development, demonstration, evaluation, and communication [3].

B. Survey and Evaluation

A survey-based evaluation was conducted to assess how different obstacle placement strategies influence player experience in the single-player mode of *Roast in Pieces*. The evaluation combines subjective questionnaire data with objective gameplay telemetry.

The study was conducted in a hybrid setting. Participants accessed the game through a downloadable build and completed all questionnaires digitally via Google Forms. Some sessions were conducted in person under supervision, while others were completed independently. In all cases, participants received standardized instructions prior to participation to ensure consistency across supervised and unsupervised sessions.

At the start of the study, participants provided informed consent and completed a background questionnaire capturing

age group, gender, gaming frequency, and prior experience with similar games.

Participants were then instructed to complete multiple playthroughs, with at least two recommended. Each playthrough was identical in gameplay but differed in the underlying placement strategy. The system ensured that each participant experienced both the adaptive and the random condition during the first two sessions.

After each playthrough, participants completed a game-play questionnaire assessing enjoyment, challenge, and overall experience using Likert-scale [4] and multiple-choice items. Some questions were inspired by the Game Experience Questionnaire (GEQ) [5], while additional custom questions targeted perceptions of the placement strategies. To ensure clear separation between conditions, two structurally identical questionnaires were implemented, with participants directed to the appropriate version based on the placement strategy.

Open-ended questions allowed participants to describe perceived patterns, gameplay strategies, and additional feedback. These qualitative responses complement the quantitative data by providing deeper insights into player experience.

The collected telemetry data serves multiple purposes. It enables the analysis of player behavior and performance, including metrics such as survival time, movement patterns, and interaction with obstacles. In addition, it supports validation of the study results by identifying outliers or irregular play sessions, for example in cases of unusually short playtime or minimal player movement. Finally, the telemetry data allows the exploration of potential relationships between objective gameplay behavior and subjective player responses, such as whether higher damage received is associated with increased perceived difficulty.

For statistical analysis, binary preference responses were collected after the second playthrough, where participants indicated whether they preferred the first or the second playthrough. These responses were analyzed using a binomial test [6], which evaluates whether the observed distribution of preferences differs from an expected equal distribution between both conditions.

Binary pattern recognition responses across the random and adaptive conditions were analyzed using the exact McNemar test [7]. This test is used for paired nominal data with dichotomous outcomes across two conditions. Due to the relatively small sample size, the exact binomial version of the McNemar test was used instead of the chi-square approximation [8].

Paired Likert-scale questionnaire responses and telemetry metrics collected across both playthroughs were analyzed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test for dependent samples.

Statistical analyses were conducted using a significance threshold of $\alpha = 0.05$. All analyses were confirmatory and based on predefined hypotheses derived from the study design. No correction for multiple comparisons was applied,

as the evaluated metrics represent distinct hypothesis-driven constructs.

Rank-biserial correlation rb was computed as a non-parametric measure of effect direction and magnitude. Positive rb values indicate higher ratings or values in the random placement strategy, whereas negative rb values indicate higher ratings or values in the adaptive placement strategy.

All collected data were checked for completeness prior to analysis.

III. RESULTS

This section presents the resulting adaptive obstacle placement system and the findings of the user study evaluating differences between the random placement strategy (condition A) and the adaptive placement strategy (condition B). Data were collected through a structured survey and gameplay telemetry. The collected data include quantitative measures of enjoyment, perceived difficulty, perceptions of obstacle placement and in-game performance.

A. Implementation of the Adaptive Placement System

The adaptive placement system follows the same high-level pipeline as the baseline approach but extends it with data-driven evaluation of candidate positions. The system is designed to replace human-driven item placement in cooperative settings by adapting obstacle locations based on observed player movement patterns. This is achieved by favoring placements that align with frequently traversed areas while maximizing the effectiveness of each obstacle’s attack range and avoiding configurations that lead to excessive difficulty or imbalanced gameplay.

Since these additional computations introduce increased runtime, both the baseline and adaptive systems display a loading screen for a fixed duration to ensure a consistent user experience across conditions despite higher computational cost.

The system operates on a grid representation of the game world. Each grid cell is classified as either traversable or non-traversable depending on whether it is occupied by level geometry such as walls, platforms, or ceilings. This representation defines the valid space for obstacle placement.

The grid representation also forms the basis of a heatmap [9], which maps 2D integer grid coordinates to a *CellData* structure. Each cell stores player visit counts over the current and two previous rounds as a three-dimensional vector. This enables obstacle placement to adapt to player movement patterns over time.

In addition, each cell maintains a persistent aggregated *lethality score*. The lethality score of an obstacle is defined by its attack interval, range, and damage output. Upon placement, the obstacle’s attack range contributes to the lethality values of affected cells. Overlapping attack ranges accumulate, approximating traversal difficulty across the map. This value is stored per cell and is used to ensure that the adaptive obstacle placement does not create regions that are excessively difficult to traverse.

The placement mechanism is structured around two nested loops, which operate on top of this representation. The outer loop iterates over the number of obstacles to be placed in the current round. For each iteration, an obstacle type is selected from a predefined subset, and a rotation is sampled uniformly from the discrete set $\{0^\circ, 90^\circ, 180^\circ, 270^\circ\}$. Candidate placement for the selected obstacle is then delegated to the inner loop.

The inner loop (Figure 2) performs stochastic sampling of candidate positions. In each iteration, a 2D position is uniformly sampled within a bounded region defining the valid placement space. A physics update is executed to correctly position the corresponding collider. A candidate is rejected if it overlaps with non-traversable geometry or if the accumulated lethality within its attack range exceeds a predefined threshold.

Candidates that satisfy these constraints are evaluated using a set of three metrics, which jointly define the scoring function used for candidate selection. The candidate with the highest resulting score, as defined in Equation 1, is selected as the final placement for the current obstacle. After all obstacles in the current round have been processed, the outer loop terminates.

The scoring function is designed to balance three competing objectives, namely alignment with player movement, avoidance of excessively dangerous regions, and effective utilization of each obstacle’s attack range. These objectives are formalized through the three metrics defined below.

The first component captures player movement history and is based on cell visitation frequency over the three most recent rounds. Player activity is aggregated across all cells covered by the attack range of candidate c . The total number of cell visits for a candidate across rounds is represented by the vector

$$\mathbf{v}_c = (v_c^{(1)}, v_c^{(2)}, v_c^{(3)}),$$

where $v_c^{(i)}$ denotes visits within the attack range of candidate c , i rounds ago.

All metrics are normalized to control the influence of each component on the final score. Combined with attributing different levels of importance to each round, this results in the normalized total cell visits defined as

$$\tilde{v}_c = w_1 \cdot \frac{v_c^{(1)}}{V_{\max}^{(1)}} + w_2 \cdot \frac{v_c^{(2)}}{V_{\max}^{(2)}} + w_3 \cdot \frac{v_c^{(3)}}{V_{\max}^{(3)}}.$$

where $V_{\max}^{(i)}$ denotes the maximum observed number of visits for round i across all candidates during evaluation and weights defined as

$$w_1 = 0.2, \quad w_2 = 0.1, \quad w_3 = 0.05, \quad w_\ell = 0.2, \quad w_u = 0.45.$$

To prevent reinforcement of already dangerous regions, a lethality constraint is introduced. The lethality score of each cell x is defined as $\ell(x)$, where ℓ_{\max} denotes the maximum possible value under system constraints. This quantifies traversal difficulty induced by previously placed obstacles. The average lethality score for a candidate is defined as

$$\tilde{\ell}_c = \sum_{x \in \mathcal{C}_c} \frac{\ell(x)}{\ell_{\max}},$$

Fig. 2. Visualization of random and adaptive placement algorithms.

which represents the normalized sum of lethality values over all affected cells, where \mathcal{C}_c denotes all grid cells covered by candidate c .

The third metric captures attack range utilization efficiency. The normalized utilization score is defined as

$$\tilde{u}_c = \frac{u_c}{u_{\max}},$$

where u_c is the raw utilization score, and u_{\max} is an empirically determined normalization constant depending on obstacle type.

The three metrics are combined into a unified scoring function defined as

$$S(c) = \tilde{v}_c - w_\ell \cdot \tilde{\ell}_c + w_u \cdot \tilde{u}_c \quad (1)$$

The subtraction of the lethality term biases the system toward placing obstacles in less dangerous regions of the map. This design choice prevents excessive clustering of hazards and contributes to improved gameplay balance. Without this constraint, obstacles would tend to accumulate in regions where players already experience difficulty, which would further increase. At the same time, assigning relatively larger weight to the attack range utilization score discourages inefficient placements. Such cases typically arise when low cell visit counts result from early player deaths, leading to poorly informed placement decisions. This mechanism helps prevent configurations in which obstacles are positioned or oriented toward walls or otherwise unused space, which would result in visually and functionally incoherent placements.

To account for differing obstacle behavior, two evaluation approaches were developed, each corresponding to a distinct obstacle group. In total, four obstacle types are considered in this game mode.

The first group comprises the *candle* and *cookie shooter* obstacles. Both emit projectiles in a linear direction until

collision with either the player or the environment occurs. Although firing patterns differ, the evaluation approach remains agnostic to these differences and treats both uniformly.

Despite dealing damage strictly along a linear trajectory, these obstacles effectively render a broader area difficult to traverse. To capture this effect, three raycasts are projected in the firing direction. The central ray represents the actual projectile path, while two additional rays are offset by one cell on each side. Each of these rays contribute to the lethality score of adjacent cells, thereby approximating the perceived danger zone more accurately, and all the covered cells are included in the computation of a candidate's number of cell visits during obstacle placement evaluation.

In practice, a sphere cast is used instead of a standard raycast. A raycast in Unity is infinitely thin and does not account for the projectile's physical size. As a result, the raycast can travel further through gaps where the actual projectile, having a non-zero radius, would already collide with the environment. This leads to an overestimation of the effective attack range and produces misleading placement evaluations.

The attack range utilization score is defined as the length of the central cast, normalized by the maximum possible cast length within the game. This maximum value was determined empirically during development and corresponds to a coverage of up to 41 cells for the candle and 47 cells for the cookie shooter. To maintain consistency with actual gameplay behavior, the auxiliary casts are constrained to the same length as the central cast, preventing extension beyond blocking elements.

The second group consists of the *flamethrower* and the *candied spinning apple*, both of which deal damage through area-based colliders. The flamethrower applies damage within a fixed region at regular intervals, while the candied apple rotates and deals damage within a circular area.

For these obstacles, the attack range is defined by their respective collider shapes. In the case of the flamethrower, the existing damage collider is used directly, covering a maximum of 15 cells. For the candied apple, an additional circular collider is introduced to represent the full rotation area, covering up to 55 cells. Upon placement, all cells covered by these colliders are assigned a lethality score and during placement evaluation, they are all included in the computation of a candidate's number of cell visits.

The attack range utilization score is determined by the number of traversable cells within the collider area. This value is normalized by dividing it by the maximum number of cells that can be covered by the collider.

B. Overview of Participants

A total of 36 participants completed the player background questionnaire, 34 completed the gameplay survey for condition A, and 36 completed the survey for condition B. This resulted in 24 participants who completed all three required questionnaires and were therefore included in the main within-subjects analysis. Participants were recruited through university networks and personal contacts. Eleven participants

(45.8%) played the Random condition first, while 13 participants (54.2%) experienced the Adaptive condition first. For in-game telemetry, complete data were available for 23 participants due to data loss in several sessions. Of these 23 participants, 15 also completed all three surveys.

Participant ages ranged from 18 to 64 years. The majority, 22 participants (91.8%), were between 18 and 34 years old. One participant (4.1%) was between 35 and 44 years, and one participant (4.1%) was between 55 and 64 years. 19 participants (79.2%) identified as male and 5 participants (20.8%) as female.

Weekly gaming time varied across participants and covered the full range of response options in the questionnaire. Four participants (16.7%) reported not playing video games at all, while another four participants (16.7%) reported playing less than one hour per week. One participant (4.2%) reported playing between 1 to 3 hours weekly.

Seven participants (29.2%) reported playing 4 to 7 hours per week, and four participants (16.7%) reported 8 to 14 hours weekly. At higher playtime levels, two participants (8.3%) reported playing 15 to 25 hours per week, while another two participants (8.3%) reported more than 25 hours weekly.

All participants reported prior experience with platformer games. 22 participants (91.8%) reported having played platformer games at least 20 times in total.

C. Player Enjoyment and Placement Strategy Preference

Player enjoyment was measured using a 6-point Likert scale (1 = “Strongly disagree”, 6 = “Strongly agree”). After experiencing both playthroughs, participants additionally indicated which playthrough they preferred overall. The hypothesis was that players would significantly prefer and enjoy the adaptive placement strategy over the random placement strategy.

1) *Enjoyment Rating*: Regarding the Likert-scale enjoyment question, the median enjoyment rating was 5.00 for both conditions. This suggests that participants generally reported high enjoyment regardless of the obstacle placement strategy.

A Wilcoxon signed-rank test revealed no statistically significant difference between the random and adaptive placement conditions ($p = 0.6579$). The rank-biserial correlation ($r_b = -0.132$) suggests only a very weak tendency towards slightly higher ratings in condition B.

The boxplots in Figure 3 further support this interpretation, showing a highly similar distribution of responses. Both conditions shared the same median, quartile ranges and whisker lengths.

These findings do not support the hypothesis that the adaptive placement strategy would lead to higher ratings of enjoyment.

2) *Direct Post-Playthrough Preference Ratings*: Participants indicated which playthrough they preferred after experiencing both conditions once.

Fig. 3. Comparison of enjoyment per placement strategy

A binomial test was conducted to evaluate the primary hypothesis that participants would prefer the adaptive condition over the random condition. The null hypothesis assumed equal preference ($H_0 : p = 0.5$). Overall, 8 out of 24 participants (33.3%) preferred the adaptive condition, while 16 participants (66.7%) preferred the random condition. This difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.1516$).

In addition, a separate binomial test was conducted to assess whether participants showed a preference for the second playthrough, regardless of condition. Here, 9 participants (37.5%) preferred the first playthrough, while 15 participants (62.5%) preferred the second playthrough. Although there was a tendency towards the second playthrough, this effect was not statistically significant ($p = 0.3075$).

Overall, there was no evidence of a systematic preference for the adaptive placement condition, nor for a general preference for the second playthrough. These results do not support the hypothesis that the adaptive placement strategy would be preferred.

D. Difficulty Rating

Participants rated the difficulty of each playthrough on a 5-point Likert scale with the ordered categories “too hard”, “hard”, “good”, “easy”, and “too easy”. The hypothesis was that there would be no significant difference in perceived difficulty between the two placement strategies.

A Wilcoxon signed-rank test revealed a statistically significant difference between the random and adaptive placement conditions ($p = 0.0050$). The rank-biserial correlation ($r_b = -0.695$) further supports this finding and indicates a strong directional effect, with participants rating condition B as more difficult than condition A.

Fig. 4. Comparison of difficulty ratings per placement strategy

The adaptive placement strategy had a median difficulty of 4.00, whereas the random placement strategy had a median difficulty of 3.00. The boxplots in Figure 4 further support this interpretation, showing a clear upward shift in the distribution for condition B.

Overall, the results indicate that the adaptive placement strategy was perceived as significantly more difficult than the random placement strategy, providing no support for the hypothesis.

E. Perceived Obstacle Placement Behavior

Perception of obstacle placement behavior was assessed using five questions. These items were designed to capture how players perceive the two placement systems and how these perceptions influence gameplay experience.

1) *Path Blocking*: This section presents the results for the question assessing how often damaging obstacles blocked the player’s path, forcing them to take damage or choose an alternative route. Participants rated this on a 6-point Likert-type scale with ordered categories “Never”, “Rarely”, “Sometimes”, “Often”, “Almost always”, and “Always”. The hypothesis was that there would be no significant differences between the two placement strategies.

A Wilcoxon signed-rank test revealed a statistically significant difference between conditions A and B ($p < 0.0001$). The rank-biserial correlation ($rb = -0.952$) indicates a strong directional effect in favor of higher ratings for condition B.

Condition B had a median rating of 4.00, while condition A had a median rating of 2.00, indicating higher perceived path blocking in the adaptive condition. The boxplots in Figure 5 also support this finding, showing a clear upward shift in condition B.

These findings do not support the stated hypothesis.

Fig. 5. Comparison of path blocking

2) *Perceived Intentionality*: Participants rated perceived intentionality on a 4-point Likert-type scale with the ordered categories “Completely random”, “Mostly random”, “Mostly purposeful and intentional”, and “Clearly purposeful and intentional”. The hypothesis was that the adaptive placement strategy would be perceived as significantly more intentional.

The median rating for the random placement strategy 3.00, while the median for the adaptive strategy was 4.00.

A Wilcoxon signed-rank test revealed a statistically significant difference between conditions ($p = 0.0060$). The rank-biserial correlation ($rb = -0.625$) indicates a clear directional effect, with condition B being perceived as more intentional than condition A.

Only 2 participants rated the adaptive condition as “mostly random”, suggesting that most participants perceived the adaptive placement as more intentional.

Overall, the adaptive placement strategy was perceived as significantly more intentional than the random placement strategy, providing support for the hypothesis.

3) *Perceived Effectiveness*: Participants rated, on a 6-point Likert-type scale, how well the obstacles were positioned such that they could actually hit the player, using the ordered categories “Not at all”, “Rarely”, “Sometimes”, “Often”, “Almost always”, and “Always”. The hypothesis was that the adaptive placement strategy would be perceived as significantly more effective.

The median rating was 4.00 for the random placement strategy and 5.00 for the adaptive strategy.

A Wilcoxon signed-rank test revealed a statistically significant difference between conditions ($p < 0.0001$). The rank-biserial correlation ($rb = -1.000$) indicates a complete

directional dominance in favor of condition B, meaning all observed differences consistently favored higher ratings for the adaptive strategy. The vast majority of responses (22 out of 24) in condition B fall into the highest category (“almost always” or “always”), indicating a strong concentration of high effectiveness ratings.

Overall, the adaptive placement strategy was perceived as significantly more effective than the random placement strategy, supporting the hypothesis.

4) *Perceived Reactivity*: Perceived reactivity was assessed using a question asking whether damaging obstacle placement appeared to react to how the player moved or played in previous rounds. Participants rated this on a 6-point Likert-type scale with the ordered categories “Not at all”, “Rarely”, “Sometimes”, “Often”, “Almost always”, and “Always”. In addition, the response option “I don’t know” was provided, as participants in a pilot study reported difficulty answering the question when no clear pattern was perceived. The hypothesis was that the adaptive placement strategy would be perceived as significantly more responsive.

Responses marked as “I don’t know” were excluded from the analysis, resulting in a sample size of 17 participants. This option was selected five times for condition A and two times for B.

The median rating was 3.00 for both conditions.

A Wilcoxon signed-rank test revealed no statistically significant difference between conditions ($p = 0.1389$). The rank-biserial correlation ($rb = -0.425$) indicates a weak tendency towards higher perceived reactivity in condition B.

Overall, there was no evidence of a meaningful difference in perceived reactivity between the two placement strategies, providing no support for the hypothesis.

5) *Recognition of Placement Patterns*: Pattern recognition was assessed by asking participants whether they noticed any patterns in the placement of damaging obstacles, using a dichotomous (yes/no) response format.

Out of 24 participants, 9 (37.5%) reported noticing patterns in the random placement strategy, while 15 (62.5%) reported noticing patterns in the adaptive placement strategy.

A McNemar test was conducted to compare paired responses between conditions and revealed no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.1094$). The paired response distribution was as follows: 7 participants reported noticing patterns in both conditions, 7 reported noticing patterns in neither condition, 2 reported patterns only in the random placement strategy, and 8 reported patterns only in the adaptive placement strategy.

This indicates a directional tendency toward increased pattern recognition in the adaptive placement strategy, although the difference was not statistically significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that players notice more placement patterns in the adaptive condition is not supported.

Fig. 6. Comparison of total player hits taken

F. Player Telemetry Metrics

Objective gameplay performance metrics were recorded during each round and across full playthroughs. These telemetry measures were used to identify quantitative differences between the random placement strategy (condition A) and the adaptive placement strategy (condition B). A total of 23 participants with complete telemetry data were included in the analysis.

1) *Total Player Hits Taken*: Players can receive hits from multiple sources in the game. Since this work focuses on differences between placement strategies, only hits caused by placed obstacles were considered.

A Wilcoxon signed-rank test revealed a statistically significant difference between the random placement strategy and the adaptive placement strategy ($p = 0.0003$). The rank-biserial correlation ($rb = -0.866$) indicates a strong directional effect towards higher hit counts in condition B.

The median increased from 10.00 in condition A to 17.00 in condition B, indicating that players were hit substantially more often in the adaptive placement condition.

The boxplots in Figure 6 further support this finding. The first quartile increased from 8.00 in condition A to 14.00 in condition B, while the third quartile increased from 12.00 to 21.50 respectively.

Overall, the results support the hypothesis that the adaptive placement strategy resulted in significantly higher numbers of player hits.

2) *Total Player Milk Collection*: Each round, players can collect up to 10 milk cartons, resulting in a maximum of 60 cartons per playthrough (six rounds). Milk collection was used as a performance-related metric reflecting player progression.

A Wilcoxon signed-rank test revealed a statistically significant

Fig. 7. Comparison of total player milk collection

cant difference between the random placement strategy and the adaptive placement strategy ($p = 0.0012$). The rank-biserial correlation ($r_b = 0.787$) indicates a strong directional effect towards higher milk collection in condition A.

The median decreased from 45.00 in condition A to 39.00 in condition B, indicating that players collected less milk in the adaptive placement condition.

The boxplots in Figure 7 further support this finding. The first quartile decreased from 39.50 in condition A to 29.00 in condition B, while the third quartile decreased from (55.50 to 44.50) respectively.

Overall, the results support the hypothesis that the adaptive placement strategy resulted in significantly less milk collection.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results are interpreted in the context of previous research. The findings are compared with related work, limitations are discussed, and directions for future research are outlined.

A. Main Findings

The results show that movement-driven adaptive obstacle placement can effectively shape player behavior and increase interaction intensity in a 2D platformer environment. By leveraging a grid-based heatmap of player movement combined with attack-range and lethality constraints, the system was able to target frequently traversed areas and produce more impactful obstacle configurations than a random baseline.

This led to consistently higher gameplay pressure in the adaptive condition. Players experienced increased perceived difficulty, more frequent collisions with obstacles, higher health loss, and reduced resource collection. These effects indicate that movement data provides a meaningful signal for guiding spatially adaptive content generation.

Despite these changes in gameplay dynamics, no corresponding increase in enjoyment or preference was observed. Both subjective enjoyment ratings and post-playthrough preferences showed no significant differences between conditions. This suggests that increased difficulty alone is insufficient to improve player experience, and may instead require closer alignment with perceived fairness or player competence.

Perceived intentionality and effectiveness of obstacle placement were significantly higher in the adaptive condition, indicating that players recognized the structured nature of the system. However, perceived system reactivity did not differ significantly, suggesting that adaptation was not clearly attributed to player behavior. This highlights a potential gap between measurable system adaptation and player interpretation of that adaptation.

Telemetry data further supports these findings, with higher obstacle hit rates and damage output in the adaptive condition, as well as increased spatial coverage of obstacle attack ranges. While some participants reported noticing more deliberate or “intentional” placement behavior, there was no evidence that players were able to reliably identify or exploit underlying patterns.

Overall, the results indicate that movement-based adaptive placement is effective for increasing difficulty and interaction density, but does not necessarily translate into improved player enjoyment or perceived system responsiveness.

B. Comparison with Previous Work

Procedural content generation (PCG) research has explored a wide range of approaches, including search-based methods, machine learning-based generation, and systems that adapt content based on player models. Many of these approaches focus on generating complete levels or large-scale structures, often replacing rather than modifying existing game environments. In parallel, Dynamic Difficulty Adjustment (DDA) and personalization systems adjust gameplay parameters based on inferred player performance and have frequently been shown to improve player satisfaction [10]–[12].

The approach in this work differs by focusing on lightweight, in-game adaptation that incrementally modifies an existing level based directly on player movement patterns. Instead of optimizing for global level structure or abstract difficulty parameters, the system uses spatial behavior traces to guide obstacle placement while preserving the underlying environment.

The results suggest that this movement-driven form of adaptation behaves differently from performance-based DDA systems. While DDA typically aims to align challenge with player skill, movement-based adaptation increases pressure based on spatial frequency, effectively targeting habitual player behavior. This leads to increased interaction intensity and perceived intentionality, but not necessarily improved enjoyment or perceived fairness.

These findings indicate that spatial adaptivity without explicit modeling of player competence may not produce the

same positive experience effects as traditional adaptive systems. Instead, it appears to function primarily as a mechanism for increasing local challenge rather than balancing overall difficulty, highlighting a distinct trade-off compared to performance-driven approaches.

C. Implications

The results of this study highlight some implications for the design of adaptive systems in games. Adaptivity alone does not guarantee improved player experience. Although the adaptive system increased challenge and interaction frequency, this did not translate into higher enjoyment. This suggests that difficulty must be carefully calibrated. The target of adaptation is also critical. The system adapts to player movement but not to player performance, increasing pressure independently of player success or failure. Future systems may benefit from incorporating performance-based signals, enabling more player-sensitive adjustments.

D. Limitations

The most important limitation of this study is the small sample size. With 24 participants for survey analyses and 23 for telemetry analyses, statistical power is limited. As a result, some effects may not have been detected reliably, and the generalizability of the findings is constrained.

A second limitation concerns the imbalance in perceived difficulty between the two placement strategies. The adaptive condition was rated as significantly more difficult, which may have influenced player enjoyment independently of the adaptive behavior itself.

Third, the study examined only a single adaptive parameter configuration. Different parameter values, such as reduced obstacle density or weaker targeting of high-traffic areas, may yield different outcomes.

Fourth, the relatively short play sessions limit the ability to assess long-term effects. Players may require more time to recognize patterns, develop strategies, or adapt their behavior in response to the system.

Lastly, the study was conducted within a single game and genre. The findings may not generalize to other types of games.

E. Further Research

Several directions for future research emerge from the present findings.

An important open question concerns player awareness of adaptive systems. If players can recognize and understand adaptive behavior, they may engage more actively with the system by attempting to counteract or exploit it. Conversely, limited transparency may reduce engagement by making the system appear arbitrary rather than reactive. This is particularly relevant because systems perceived as arbitrary can also

be interpreted as unfair, which may negatively impact player experience and satisfaction. Studies that explicitly manipulate both the presence of adaptivity and its visibility would help clarify this relationship.

Future studies should also consider difficulty-matched comparisons between adaptive and non-adaptive systems. In the present work, the adaptive condition increased overall challenge, which makes it difficult to separate the effects of adaptivity from the effects of difficulty alone. Matching difficulty across conditions would allow a more precise evaluation of whether adaptive placement itself contributes to player experience.

Extended playtests would allow a more comprehensive evaluation of how player experience evolves over time. With prolonged interaction, players may develop strategies, recognize patterns in the system, and engage more meaningfully with adaptive behavior, effects that may not emerge in short-term sessions.

Finally, the approach of adapting spatial elements based on player movement could be extended to other 2D games. Investigating its effectiveness in different gameplay contexts would help identify the boundaries of spatial adaptivity and clarify in which types of games it provides the most value.

V. CONCLUSION

These results indicate that adaptive spatial obstacle placement can increase perceived difficulty, environmental pressure, and player interaction, but does not necessarily improve overall player enjoyment. This suggests that adaptivity in procedural content generation must be carefully aligned with player performance rather than solely reacting to movement patterns. Consequently, more sophisticated player-aware PCG approaches may be required to translate increased engagement and challenge into improved player experience.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Fridolin Ernst conducted the research as part of the master's thesis, including study conception, data collection, analysis, and drafting of the manuscript. The full master's thesis is available from the library of the UAS Technikum Wien. Christoph Redl supervised the research process on a regular basis, provided conceptual guidance, critically reviewed the manuscript, and approved the final version for publication.

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